

Blockchain Evolution from 1.0 to 4.0 Abstract

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1. Introduction

Blockchain has gained lot of importance from the last one decade in all the sectors of the industry especially in banking and finance. Cryptocurrency is also playing a prominent role in the transformation of economy and cross border payments.

2. Aim

To discuss and explain the evolution of Blockchain.

3. Conclusions

According to study of evolution of blockchain we can predict a huge transformation in the economy for a better cause.

Author biography

Srinivasa Raju V has completed his Masters and pursuing Ph.D at the age of 45 years from JNTU. He is the director of Alykas Innovatiions Pvt. Ltd, a blockchain startup in India. He has published more than 4 papers in reputed journals and has implemented 2 consensus algorithms for Ethereum and BitCoin.

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